

Driver Drowsiness System with Early Detection

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Abstract— Drowsiness or fatigue poses a significant threat to road safety, often leading to fatal accidents. Timely warning systems for drowsy drivers are crucial in preventing such incidents. Various detection methods, including monitoring facial expressions and analyzing physiological and vehicular data, aim to assess driver drowsiness detection with early detection.

Keywords— Drowsiness detection, Driver Monitoring, Sleepiness detection, Eye tracking, real time detection, Driver assistance system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drowsiness or fatigue poses a significant threat to road safety, resulting in severe injuries, fatalities, and economic losses. Increased drowsiness deteriorates driving performance, leading to serious road accidents. The U.S. National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) reports that drowsy driving contributes to almost 100,000 road accidents and over 1,500 deaths annually. Various factors such as lack of sleep, long journeys, restlessness, alcohol consumption, and mental pressure contribute to driver fatigue, each capable of causing disastrous consequences.

Moreover, the prevalence of road rage exacerbates stress on drivers, further compromising their alertness. Traditional transportation systems are insufficient to address these hazards adequately. Embedding automatic fatigue detection systems into vehicles presents a promising solution to prevent deadly accidents. These systems continuously analyze drivers' attention levels and alert them before serious threats to road safety arise.

Recognizing the urgency of addressing fatigue-related hazards on roads, researchers have developed various methods to detect driver drowsiness, each with its own benefits and limitations. To conduct a comprehensive review of Drowsiness Detection Techniques (DDT) and appropriate classification methods, we devised search strings to gather relevant information from reputable journals and conferences. Employing a multi-stage selection criteria and assessment procedure, we filtered 41 research papers from a detailed search of 1020.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Drowsiness or fatigue is a major cause of road accidents and has significant implications for road safety. Several deadly accidents can be prevented if the drowsy drivers are warned in time. A variety of drowsiness detection methods exist that monitor the drivers' drowsiness state while driving and alarm the drivers if they are not concentrating on driving. The relevant features can be extracted from facial expressions such as yawning, eye closure, and head movements for inferring the level of drowsiness[1]. The biological condition of the drivers' body, as well as vehicle behaviour, is analyzed for driver drowsiness detection. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the existing methods of driver drowsiness detection and presents a detailed analysis of widely used classification techniques in this regard.

Drivers who do not take regular breaks when driving long distances run a high risk of becoming drowsy a state which they often fail to recognize early enough according to the experts. Studies show that around one quarter of all serious motorway accidents are attributable to sleepy drivers in need of a rest, meaning that drowsiness causes more road accidents than drink-driving[2]. Attention assist can warn of inattentiveness and drowsiness in an extended speed range and notify drivers of their current state of fatigue and the driving time since the last break, offers adjustable sensitivity and, if a warning is emitted, indicates nearby service areas in the COMMAND navigation System.

Drowsiness in drivers has become a serious cause of concern due to the occurrences of a large number of fatalities on the road each year. Lives of pedestrians as well as passengers are put to risk as drivers tend to fall asleep at the steering wheel. In the recent past, many researchers have paid attention to the problem of drowsiness detection [3] since safe roads and safe driving are of paramount concern to all societies. This research work has led to the development of several novel and effective methods in detecting drivers' drowsiness. These include 1. Vehicle based methods, 2. Behavioral methods and 3. Physiological methods. Since wake-sleep is an intermediate state between two physiologically dissimilar states, physiological signals can define this transition more accurately when compared to approaches that fall in other categories. This paper focuses on the role of physiological signals in detecting driver's drowsiness level. The proposed methods measure the physiological signals by means of various sensors, which monitor the driver's physiological parameters on a continual basis.

Drowsiness and Fatigue of drivers are amongst the significant causes of road accidents. Every year, they increase the amounts of deaths and fatalities in-juries globally. In this paper, a module for Advanced Driver assistance System (ADAS) is presented to reduce the number of accidents due to drivers fatigue and hence increase the transportation safety; this system deals with automatic driver drowsiness detection based on visual information and Artificial Intelligence. We proposed an algorithm to locate, track, and analyze both the drivers face and eyes to measure percentage of eye douser, a scientifically supported measure of drowsiness associated with slow eye closure.

Driver drowsiness detection is a critical aspect of ensuring road safety, particularly as fatigue can significantly impair driving performance and increase the risk of accidents. Behavioral measures, such as facial expressions, offer valuable cues for inferring levels of drowsiness [5]. Facial features like eye blinks, head movements, and yawning provide rich data that can be leveraged for drowsiness detection. However, developing a reliable and accurate drowsiness detection system poses considerable challenges, necessitating the use of robust algorithms. Over the years, a plethora of techniques have been explored to detect driver drowsiness. With the advent of deep learning, there is a renewed interest in revisiting these algorithms to assess their efficacy in drowsiness detection. In this context, this paper conducts a comprehensive review of machine learning techniques applied to drowsiness detection. Specifically, it focuses on support vector machines (SVM), convolutional neural networks (CNN), and hidden Markov models (HMM).

The advancement of computing technology over the years has provided assistance to drivers mainly in the form of intelligent vehicle systems. Driver fatigue is a significant factor in a large number of vehicle accidents. Thus, driver drowsiness detection has been considered a major potential area so as to prevent a huge number of sleep induced road accidents. This paper proposes a vision based intelligent algorithm to detect driver drowsiness [6]. Previous approaches are generally based on blink rate, eye closure, yawning, eye brow shape and other hand engineered facial features. The proposed algorithm makes use of features learnt using convolutional neural network so as to explicitly capture various latent facial features and the complex non- linear feature interactions. A softmax layer is used to classify the driver as drowsy or non-drowsy. This system is hence used for warning the driver of drowsiness or in attention to prevent traffic accidents. We present both qualitative and quantitative results to substantiate the claims made in the paper.

The advance of computing technology has provided the means for building intelligent vehicle systems. Drowsy driver detection system [7] is one of the potential applications of intelligent vehicle systems. Previous approaches to drowsiness detection primarily make pre- assumptions about the relevant behaviour, focusing on blink rate, eye closure, and yawning. Here we employ machine learning to datamined actual human behaviour during drowsiness episodes. Automatic classifiers for 30 facial actions from the Facial Action Coding system were developed using machine learning on a separate database of spontaneous expressions. These facial actions include blinking and yawn motions, as well as a number of other facial movements. In addition, head motion was collected through automatic eye tracking and an accelerometer. These measures were passed to learning-based classifiers such as Ad boost and multinomial ridge regression. The system was able to predict sleep and crash episodes during a driving computer game with 96% accuracy within sub- jects and above 90% accuracy across subjects. This is the highest prediction rate reported to date for detecting real drowsiness. Moreover, the analysis revealed new information about human behaviour during drowsy driving.

The face, an important part of the body, conveys a lot of information. When a driver is in a state of fatigue, the facial expressions, e.g., the frequency of blinking and yawning, are different from those in the normal state. In this paper, we propose a system called DriCare [8], which detects the drivers' fatigue status, such as yawning, blinking, and duration of eye closure, using video images, without equipping their bodies with devices. Owing to the shortcomings of previous algorithms, we introduce a new face-tracking algorithm to improve the tracking accuracy. Further, we designed a new detection method for facial regions based on 68 key points. Then we use these facial regions to evaluate the drivers' state. By combining the features of the eyes and mouth, DriCare can alert the driver using a fatigue warning. The experimental results showed that DriCare achieved around 92% accuracy.

Driver drowsiness/fatigue is an important cause of combination-unit truck crashes. Drowsy driver detection methods can form the basis of a system to potentially reduce accidents related to drowsy driving. We report on efforts performed at the Carnegie Mellon Driving Research Center to develop such in vehicle driver monitoring systems [9]. Commercial motor vehicle truck drivers were studied in actual fleet operations. The drivers operated vehicles that were equipped to measure vehicle performance and driver psychophysiological data. Based on this work, two drowsiness detection methods are being considered. The first is a video-based system that measures PERCLOS, a scientifically supported measure of drowsiness associated with slow eye closure. The second detection method is based on a model to estimate PERCLOS based on vehicle performance data. A non-parametric (neural network) model was used to estimate PERCLOS using measures associated with lane keeping, steering wheel movements and lateral acceleration of the vehicle.

It is a difficult problem to make drivers drowsiness detection meet the needs of real time in embedded system; meanwhile, there are still some unsolved problems like drivers' head tilted and size of eye image not large enough. This paper proposes an efficient method to solve these problems for eye state identification of drivers' drowsiness detection [10] in embedded system which based on image processing techniques. This method break traditional way of drowsiness detection to make it real time, it utilizes face detection and eye detection to initialize the location of driver's eyes; after that an object tracking method is used to keep track of the eyes; finally, we can identify drowsiness state of driver with PERCLOS by identified eye state. Experiment results show that it makes good agreement with analysis.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

Detecting driver drowsiness typically involves monitoring various factors such as eye movements, head position, steering behaviour, and vehicle speed. Here's a basic outline of a model for driver drowsiness detection:

Figure 1- Flowchart of how the model works

The proposed driver drowsiness detection system utilizes a combination of computer vision and machine learning techniques to monitor and classify driver behavior in real-time. Data is collected using a camera mounted on the dashboard, capturing the driver's face and eye movements. The captured images are preprocessed to extract facial landmarks and calculate features such as eye closure duration, head pose, and blink frequency.

A. Dataset

Datasets for driver drowsiness detection play a crucial role in training and evaluating machine learning models. These datasets typically consist of images or videos of drivers captured in various driving conditions, along with labels indicating their state (e.g., alert, drowsy). A well-annotated dataset enables the development of models that can accurately distinguish between different states based on facial cues and driving behavior.

Figure 2- The proposed method: an overview of the general structure

Model:

Figure 3: Models

Model: "mobilenet_1.00_224"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	[(None, 224, 224, 3)]	0
conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	864
conv1_bn (BatchNormalization)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	128
conv1_relu (ReLU)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	0
conv_dw_1 (DepthwiseConv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	288
conv_dw_1_bn (BatchNormalization)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	128
conv_dw_1_relu (ReLU)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	0

Table 1: Model

IV. RESULT

Deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), excels in feature learning from visual data. CNNs iteratively adjust parameters to learn hierarchical representations, capturing intricate patterns directly from input images. Figure 5 showcases learned weights at different layers, embodying essential features for subsequent tasks. These automatic feature extraction capabilities empower CNNs to efficiently analyze image data, revolutionizing various applications with their ability to discern complex patterns and structures.

Validation Accuracy: 92.60%

Validation Loss: 0.1240

The input being provided to the first layer and the output (drowsy/non drowsy label) provided to the output of the last layer, all weights are learnt, all the learned weights acts a learned feature detectors for driver drowsiness and these feature detectors are convolved with input images to produce the final features used for classification. The dataset collected from the 30 different subjects in diverse conditions was divided into training and validation data randomly. All the extracted faces from the frames were labeled manually as drowsy and non-drowsy. The trained classifier worked efficiently as it gave 92.33% validation accuracy. Considering the fact that a car is driven by the same single person most of the time, an experiment is carried out as the driver is made to drive his vehicle for hours together in artificially simulated conditions and a training video is recorded and manually labeled later. Later, the test is done on the same driver. The average accuracy within subjects was 88%. Furthermore, another experiment was carried out in which we train the classifier on a set of subjects and the testing is done on absolutely different variety of people having different physical and facial characteristics. A satisfactory average result of 78% accuracy across subjects was found in such a case. Thus, the proposed deep learning based classifier detects the driver drowsiness based on only visual facial features efficiently on a diverse dataset.

Test	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
1	0.5125	0.4500
2	0.5000	0.5000
3	0.5625	0.5000
4	0.5625	0.3500
5	0.5500	0.3000
6	0.5375	0.6500
7	0.5000	0.5000
8	0.4000	0.4500
9	0.5500	0.5000
10	0.5500	0.6500

Figure 4- Training & testing accuracy graph of the proposed model

2. Model Loss:

The graph depicting model loss provides insights into the convergence and optimization of the CNN architecture during training. A decreasing loss curve indicates an effective reduction in prediction errors over epochs, signifying improved model performance. Conversely, erratic or increasing loss curves may indicate issues such as overfitting or underfitting, necessitating further investigation and adjustments in model architecture or training parameters.

Figure 5- Training & testing loss graph of the proposed model

These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the CNN model in accurately classifying drowsiness, with a high validation accuracy indicating its capability to generalize well to unseen data. The low validation loss further validates the robustness of the model in minimizing prediction errors.

The model accuracy and loss visualizations provide additional insights into the performance of the CNN model, offering a graphical representation of its classification accuracy and convergence during training and evaluation.

Drowsy

Not Drowsy

**Figure 6- Sample prediction results for Driver
Drowsiness Detection with early detection**

Figure 6 shows samples that were taken from the dataset randomly and labeled with actual and predicted labels using the proposed model for Driver drowsiness detection with early detection. As can be seen, the constructed model usually had no difficulty in identifying drowsiness. For example, the first sample image was labeled correctly with a 99.96% probability.

	AU	Name	A'
Subj1	45	Blink	.94
	17	Chin Raise	.85
	30	Jaw sideways	.84
	7	Lid tighten	.81
	39	Nostril compress	.79
Subj2	2	Outer brow raise	.91
	45	Blink	.80
	17	Chin Raise	.76
	15	Lip corner depress	.76
	11	Nasolabial furrow	.76
Subj3	45	Blink	.86
	9	Nose wrinkle	.78
	25	Lips part	.78
	1	Inner brow raise	.74
	20	Lip stretch	.73
Subj4	45	Blink	.90
	4	Brow lower	.81
	15	Lip corner depress	.81
	7	Lid tighten	.80
	39	Nostril Compress	.74

Table 2: The top 5 most discriminant action units for discriminating alert from non- alert states for each of the four subjects. A' is area under the ROC curve.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a comprehensive review of current proposals utilizing sensors for measuring physiological signals in drowsiness detection. While various methods exist, our focus is specifically on schemes based on physiological signals. Through extensive literature analysis, we identify key parameters characterizing drowsiness, detailing their advantages and limitations practically. We emphasize the improvement of sensing materials like silver/silver chloride, gold/gold chloride, titanium, nickel, aluminum, and stainless steel, particularly for their gel-free usability. Despite the availability of dry electrodes for data collection during driving, intrusive signal collection remains prevalent due to its precision. Inter-individual variability poses a significant challenge for commercializing physiological signal-based drowsiness detection systems, hindered by the lack of standardization in experimental settings. Addressing this, future studies should establish uniform experimental protocols across different countries to assess physiological parameters' impacts under diverse conditions.

VI. REFERENCES

The template will number citations consecutively within brackets [1]. The sentence punctuation follows the bracket [2]. Refer simply to the reference number, as in [3]—do not use “Ref. [3]” or “reference [3]” except at the beginning of a sentence: “Reference [3] was the first ...”

Number footnotes separately in superscripts. Place the actual footnote at the bottom of the column in which it was cited. Do not put footnotes in the abstract or reference list. Use letters for table footnotes.

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For papers published in translation journals, please give the English citation first, followed by the original foreign-language citation [6].

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